

EPITHELIAL TUMORS OF THE EYELID.

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Relevance of the topic: Today, among ophthalmological diseases, eyelid epithelial tumors account for approximately 85–90% of all eyelid tumors. Although benign tumors are also common among them, malignant tumors (especially basal cell carcinoma) are one of the most common diseases encountered in clinical practice. In general, solar radiation, environmental factors, decreased immunity in the human body, and age factors play an important role in the development of these tumors. Therefore, in-depth study of the morphological and immunohistochemical characteristics of epithelial tumors is an important role in the development of early diagnosis and effective treatment tactics.

The purpose of the study: to study the clinical, morphological and immunohistochemical characteristics of epithelial tumors of the eyelid and to evaluate their diagnostic value.

Research materials and methods: Biopsies and post-surgical materials from patients who underwent surgery for eyelid tumors were studied as research materials. Histological examination, hematoxylin-eosin staining, immunohistochemical analysis using markers such as Ki-67, p53, CK (cytokeratins). Morphometric parameters were assessed using microscopic digital software.

Research results: According to the results of the study, the most common type of epithelial eyelid tumors is basal cell carcinoma, which is mainly observed in elderly patients. Papilloma, keratoacanthoma, and seborrheic keratoses predominated among benign tumors. Morphologically, malignant tumors showed cellular atypia, increased mitoses, and disruption of the basement membrane. High levels of Ki-67 expression indicated proliferative activity of the tumor. Increased levels of the p53 marker were found to be associated with genetic damage and malignancy processes.

Conclusion: In conclusion, it can be said that 1. Basal cell carcinoma is the most common malignant tumor among epithelial tumors of the eyelid. 2. Morphological and immunohistochemical studies are important for early diagnosis. 3. Markers such as Ki-67 and p53 are reliable indicators for assessing the proliferative activity of a tumor and the degree of malignancy. 4. The results obtained will serve to improve differential diagnosis and treatment tactics in clinical practice.

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